

»Surveil and Punish« – Tracking and Control of the Research Life Cycle¹

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Abstract: Since the German Research Foundation's Information Paper 2021, data tracking in science has been widely discussed. However, comprehensive concepts on how to remedy this threat to scientific autonomy and integrity, for example by strengthening digital sovereignty, are not given, nor is the grip of the relevant economic actors on the entire research cycle adequately addressed. This paper looks at scientific workflows and their undermining by data-based business models.

Keywords: data tracking, surveillance capitalism, scientific autonomy

1 Prehistory

When Michel Foucault published *Surveiller et punir* in 1975,² his analysis of disciplinary power achieved a long and considerable history of impact. The description of dispositives as a linkage of discursive and institutional moments allowed him to move from his previous discourse-analytical consideration of shorting elements such as the »author«³ or the »discipline«⁴ to the strategies of power. Dispositives show themselves to be very productive in his consideration and produce effects that can be quite contrary to their discursive statements:⁵ The clinic dispositive talks about »health« and »healing« and produces patients, the prison dispositive talks about »improvement« and »resocialization« and produces delinquents – etc. What is decisive is the considerable, if not total, asymmetry of power that dispositifs create, as can be seen in Foucault's prime example, Bentham's *Panopticon*.

For Bentham, the Panopticon was to be the ideal type of prison: The cells were arranged in a circle around an observation tower for the guard, who could thus see all prisoners but not be seen himself. The *unobservable observer* was the central principle of the Panopticon, because the prisoner had to assume that he could at least be observed at any time, even if the guard was looking at other prisoners or the tower was not occupied at all. The surrender to the total asymmetry of power should, according to Bentham's conception, have a behavior-shaping effect - the prisoner would refrain from all undesirable movements and internalize the disciplinary regime.

¹ This text is a machine-based translation of my article »Überwachen und Strafen« in order to provide easier access for non-German speaking interested parties, also the german language quotes were therefore transferred and the sources not adapted. Consider this version a »post-print derivative« and please refer to the original in case of references or citations: Siems, Renke: »Überwachen und Strafen« – Tracking und Kontrolle des Forschungszyklus. *ABI Technik* 2023; 43(2): 86–9; <https://doi.org/10.1515/abitech-2023-0016>

² Foucault, Michel: *Surveiller et punir*. Naissance de la prison. Paris: Gallimard 1975.

³ Cf. Michel Foucault: »Was ist ein Autor?« In: M.F.: *Schriften zur Literatur*. Frankfurt/M.: Fischer 1988, pp. 7 - 31.

⁴ Cf. Michel Foucault: *Die Ordnung des Diskurses*. Frankfurt/M.: Fischer 1991.

⁵ Cf. the explanation in Clemens Kammler: *Michel Foucault. Eine kritische Analyse seines Werks*. Bonn: Bouvier 1986, pp. 155 - 175.

Fig. 1: Panoptic prison in Cuba from the time of the Machado dictatorship.⁶

Foucault's prominent emphasis on the panopticon probably contributed to the fact that in the age of digitalization it was again increasingly the subject of discussion - not least because the behavior-shaping power could now also be empirically proven here, for example, in the area of video surveillance⁷ even if it proves to be not very sustainable as a metaphor for digital power strategies on closer examination.⁸ But Shoshana Zuboff also analyzes the panoptic threat behind the Internet corporations' discourses of do-gooderism in her observation of surveillance capitalism⁹. In a very practical way, the tool *Panopticlick* by the Electronic Frontier Foundation¹⁰ takes the big monitoring platforms out of their unobservability by examining the browser features and sensitizes them to the power imbalance that they execute through tracking.

⁶ Inside one of the prison buildings at Presidio Modelo, Isla de la Juventud, Cuba. By Friman, CC BY-SA 3.0 <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=2410607>

⁷ Rothmann, Robert: Video Surveillance and the Right of Access: The empirical proof of panoptical asymmetries. *Surveillance and Society* Vol. 15, No. 2 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.24908/ss.v15i2.6029>

⁸ Cf. Gehring, Petra: The Inverted Eye. Panopticon and Panopticism, Revisited. *Foucault Studies* Nr. 23 (2017): 46–63. <http://dx.doi.org/10.22439/fs.v0i0.534>

⁹ See Shoshana Zuboff: *The Age of Surveillance Capitalism. The Fight for a Human Future at the New Frontier of Power*. London: Profile Books 2019.

¹⁰ Cf. Electronic Frontier Foundation: Panopticlick 3.0. <https://www.eff.org/de/deeplinks/2017/11/panopticlick-30>

2 Tracking

Data tracking in science has been widely discussed¹¹ in the literature in German-speaking countries at least since the DFG's information paper,¹² *ABI Technik* has also already dedicated a special issue to the subject.¹³ Michael Freiberg thereby deepened the knowledge of third-party tracking technologies used by publishers,¹⁴ while the interview with the Hessian State Commissioner for Data Protection and Freedom of Information, Andreas Roßnagel, focused on legal issues with clear words:

„Libraries and universities must prevent violations of fundamental rights through the selection of their contractual partners and the agreements with them. In case of doubt, they are not allowed to use services whose compliance with fundamental rights they cannot ensure.“¹⁵

In contrast, there is not really much evidence of the implementation of this legal obligation - and obligation to their patrons - to date. A current practical guide to open access transformation and library acquisition,¹⁶ for example, makes no mention whatsoever of this problem, although it can be assumed that publishers are highly motivated to track information behavior, especially in the open access sector.¹⁷ The Open Access recommendations of the German *Wissenschaftsrat* emphasize in a short section the chances of such *science analytics*, if only the rules were followed.¹⁸ The statement of the initiative »Digital Information« of the Alliance of German Science Organizations on transformation contracts provides equally cautious and incomplete target formulations,¹⁹ while the further circumstances of the publication in Brems's opinion turned out to be quite astonishing.²⁰

¹¹ See the collection of the Open Access Bureau Berlin, <https://www.zotero.org/groups/2316312/oabb>, and on the website »Stop Tracking Science«, <https://stoptrackingscience.eu/>.

¹² Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft: Datentracking in der Wissenschaft: Aggregation und Verwendung bzw. Verkauf von Nutzungsdaten durch Wissenschaftsverlage. Bonn: DFG 2021. https://www.dfg.de/download/pdf/foerderung/programme/lis/datentracking_papier_de.pdf

¹³ *ABI Technik* Vol. 42, Issue 2 (2022).

¹⁴ Michael Freiberg: Third-Party Tracking at Springer and Wiley. Analysis and Outlook. *ABI Technik* Vol. 42, Issue 2 (2022), pp. 96 - 104. <https://doi.org/10.1515/abitech-2022-0017>

¹⁵ Roßnagel, Alexander: Third-Party-Tracking – ein Problem aus Sicht des Datenschutzes? Interview mit Prof. Dr. Alexander Roßnagel, Hessischer Beauftragter für Datenschutz und Informationsfreiheit. *ABI Technik*, Vol. 42, Issue 2 (2022), pp. 105 - 107. <https://doi.org/10.1515/abitech-2022-0018>

¹⁶ Rösch, Henriette, Geschuhn, Kai, Barbers, Irene et al: Open Access ermöglichen: Open Access-Transformation und Erwerbung in wissenschaftlichen Bibliotheken – ein praktischer Leitfaden. Zenodo 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6090208>

¹⁷ Cf. Siems, Renke: Das Lesen der Anderen. Die Auswirkungen von User Tracking auf Bibliotheken. *O-Bib. Das offene Bibliotheksjournal*. Vol. 9, Issue 1 (2022), pp. 1-25. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5282/o-bib/5797>

¹⁸ Wissenschaftsrat: Empfehlungen zur Transformation des wissenschaftlichen Publizierens zu Open Access (Drs. 9477-22). Bonn: Wissenschaftsrat 2022, p. 47f. <https://doi.org/10.57674/fyrc-vb61> Currently, a working group of the *Wissenschaftsrat* is working on the topic of security and sovereignty in the digital space and is also revisiting the issue of tracking.

¹⁹ Pampel, Heinz, Bertelmann, Roland, Hillenkötter, Kristine et al: Empfehlungen für transformative Zeitschriftenverträge mit Publikationsdienstleistern. Handreichung der Schwerpunktinitiative "Digitale Information" der Allianz der deutschen Wissenschaftsorganisationen vor dem Hintergrund der Umsetzung der Open-Access-Strategie 2021-2025 der Allianz der deutschen Wissenschaftsorganisationen, Schwerpunktinitiative "Digitale Information" der Allianz der deutschen Wissenschaftsorganisationen. Potsdam: Deutsches GeoForschungsZentrum 2022, p. 8. <https://doi.org/10.48440/allianzoa.045>

²⁰ Cf. Brems, Björn: Große Enttäuschung und ernste Fragen. *Wiarda Blog* 15.12.2022, <https://www.jmwiarda.de/2022/12/16/gro%C3%9Fentt%C3%A4uschung-und-ernste-fragen/>

The bottom line is that after the initial push by the DFG, which also mentioned the potentially significant personal risk for researchers and the possibility of industrial espionage, other key players in the information industry do not seem to have adopted this risk analysis in the same way, but rather seem to be inclined to classify it among the many other contractual adversities that are known from negotiations with the major publishers.²¹ This underestimation of tracking is common in many sectors - »It's just advertising« - and is rejected in no uncertain terms by digital advertising technology expert Bob Hoffman:

„The worst consequences of tracking are not that it makes *advertising* worse, it's that it makes *other things* so dangerous. What most people don't understand is that the tracking-based data collected by and for advertisers is also used:

- To create algorithms that have the effect of polarizing us and driving wedges into society.
- By malefactors to spread misinformation and lies in specific directions and undermining confidence in elections, democratic institutions and scientific findings.
- By criminals to extract tens of billions of dollars illegally from the programmatic advertising ecosystem.“²²

Hoffman exemplifies this with the situation in which the Supreme Court overturned the Roe v. Wade ruling, and at one blow the data amassed by the tracking industry became a massive threat, be it location data, Facebook Pixel and other trackers on hospital websites, or usage data from period apps, for example - and messages exchanged on Facebook promptly became the undoing of a pregnant seventeen-year-old and her mother. An industry that had already collected an average of 72 million data points from a 13-year-old child should be treated with every due caution, Hoffman said, regardless of individual technical expertise – „you don't have to be an automotive engineer to understand that a truck can run you over.“²³ In view of this situation, the European Commission has presented an extensive study to fundamentally reform digital advertising.²⁴

3 Workbenches

As early as 2020, Claudio Aspesi and Amy Brand pointed out the danger that open access could also lead to lock-in effects if the provider, instead of having sole access to package licenses for content, were now able to bundle ever larger parts of the publication volume with itself through privileged transformation contracts, thereby linking access, analysis, hosting, assessment, research data, and many more services.²⁵ What Aspesi and Brand therefore call „the next battleground,“ namely the struggle for infrastructural sovereignty in order to be able to

²¹ Internationally, the reactions are in part much clearer, cf. e.g. CAUL Procurement Guidance Statement to Vendors on Privacy and Unauthorized Access Processes; <https://www.caul.edu.au/news/caul-procurement-guidance-statement-vendors-privacy-and-unauthorised-access-processes>

²² Hoffman, Bob: AdScam. How Online Advertising Gave Birth to One of History's Greatest Frauds, and Became a Threat to Democracy. Oakland: Type A Group 2022, p. 20.

²³ Hoffman 2022, p. 8.

²⁴ European Commission, Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology, C. Armitage, N. Botton, L. Dejeu-Castang u. a.: Study on the impact of recent developments in digital advertising on privacy, publishers and advertisers: final report. Brüssel: Publications Office of the European Union, 2023. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2759/29467>

²⁵ Aspesi, Claudio; Brand, Ami: In pursuit of open access, open access is not enough. Science vol. 368, No. 6491 (2022), pp. 574 - 577. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aba3763>

continue to secure scientific autonomy at least to some extent, is described somewhat dramatically in a recent account:

„It is becoming increasingly clear that the core functions of higher education are destined to be quantified and that this data will be harvested, curated, and repackaged through a variety of enterprise management platforms. All aspects of the academic lifecycle, such as research production, publication, distribution, impact determination, citation analysis, grant award trends, graduate student research topic, and more can be sold, analyzed, and gamed to an unhealthy degree.“²⁶

24-AUG-2021	UserDocumentUpdated	{\source\:"The Lancet Psychiatry\;"typeId\:"1\;"profileId\:"0e19adad-044f-372c-b5d0-5db1d1591d3a\;"doi\:"10.1016/s2215-0366(21)00283-2\;"year\:"2021\;"isAuthor\:"false\;"}
24-AUG-2021	OpenPdfInInternalViewer	{\Online\:"true\;"}
24-AUG-2021	UserDocumentUpdated	{\source\:"Philosophy of Science\;"typeId\:"1\;"profileId\:"0e19adad-044f-372c-b5d0-5db1d1591d3a\;"doi\:"10.1086/392759\;"year\:"2000\;"isAuthor\:"false\;"}
24-AUG-2021	UserDocumentCreated	{\typeId\:"1\;"profileId\:"0e19adad-044f-372c-b5d0-5db1d1591d3a\;"year\:"2021\;"isAuthor\:"false\;"}
23-AUG-2021	UserDocumentCreated	{\source\:"Philosophy of Science\;"typeId\:"1\;"profileId\:"0e19adad-044f-372c-b5d0-5db1d1591d3a\;"doi\:"10.1086/392759\;"year\:"2000\;"isAuthor\:"false\;"}
23-AUG-2021	OpenPdfInInternalViewer	{\Online\:"true\;"}
23-AUG-2021	DocumentAnnotationCreated	{\annotationId\:"8fa03f09-c665-4544-86e9-86725796c9d9\;"}

Fig. 2: Recorded usage data of a Mendeley account

This networking, consolidation and evaluation of science-related data is based on the outstanding revenues in the publishing business and was therefore already analyzed years ago by Roger Schonfeld in relation to publishing as the coming »supercontinent«,²⁷ but concerns not only publications, but the entire research cycle. The focus is always on access to the specific person and his or her behavior, as Eiko Fried was able to make clear - the »Hotel Elsevier« keeps precise records with a table that comprises 213,000 lines for the Mendeley usage of a few years alone.²⁸

An even more detailed impression can be gained by sorting the news on acquisitions and takeovers of recent years according to the individual stages of the research cycle. Alejandro

²⁶ Koivisto, Joseph; Sly, Jordan: *Publication and data surveillance in academia*. Research Information Yearbook 2022/2023. <https://www.researchinformation.info/feature/publication-and-data-surveillance-academia>

²⁷ Cf. Schonfeld, Roger C.: *The Supercontinent of Scholarly Publishing?*, The Scholarly Kitchen 03.05.2018, <https://scholarlykitchen.sspnet.org/2018/05/03/supercontinent-scholarly-publishing/>

²⁸ Eiko Fried: *Welcome to Hotel Elsevier: You can check out any time you like ... not*. Eiko Fried Blog, 09.05.2022, <https://eiko-fried.com/welcome-to-hotel-elsevier-you-can-check-out-any-time-you-like-not/> Image used with permission of the author.

Posada and George Chen have done this with a focus on Elsevier,²⁹ Bianca Kramer and Jeroen Bosman have looked at a whole range of media companies in this way in the »101 Innovations« project.³⁰ This shows that the »mergeritis« among the market leaders of the former publishers has already led to the creation of complete ecosystems that researchers no longer need to leave at all - and certainly should not, because as with social media and their »doom scrolling,« longer presence means more data, more observation, and more exploitation.

Fig. 3: Workbenches sorted by providers³¹

²⁹ Posada, Alejandro; Chen, George: *Publishers are increasingly in control of scholarly infrastructure and why we should care*. The Knowledge G.A.P. 20.09.2017, <https://knowledgegap.org/index.php/sub-projects/rent-seeking-and-financialization-of-the-academic-publishing-industry/preliminary-findings/>

³⁰ Kramer, Bianca; Bosman, Jeroen: *Innovations in Scholarly Communications. Changing Research Workflows*, <https://101innovations.wordpress.com/workflows/>

³¹ Graphic by Björn Brems based on Bianca Kramer and Jeroen Bosman (see footnote 30), <https://stoptrackingscience.eu/background-information/>. Graphic used with permission of the author.

The economist Philip Mirowski analyzes this development as a neoliberal attack on science, whereby, after an already long history of commercialization of research since the 2010s by platform capitalism, a re-engineering of the whole process would be observed.³² The goal would be the control of science by platforms instead of just individual »IP bits« - a point Schonfeld had already taken up in his description of the *supercontinent*: the disintegration of content by copyright law also imposed barriers on exploitation in the past, the shift to open access, on the other hand, would allow materials to be bundled, analyzed, and covered with overarching layers of exploitation products on a completely different scale. »Open« alone can thus also come to mean something ambiguous, namely, as open to influence, interference, and the market. Mirowski takes up this point by casting Open Science as a whole as the Big 5 publishers' subtle revenge on science activists. The companies would have been fully aware of the foreseeable exhaustion of their traditional business model, and they would now again be several steps ahead of the scientists, buying up, assembling, monetizing, and keeping under control the entire infrastructure of the research process under the public agenda of Open Science.

Open Science in this market-like controlled form then completely overturns the previous understanding of science and above all the corresponding practice, recognizable in the position of the researchers. The precariously employed scientists of *#IchbinHanna*³³ are in the perspective neither a mere accident nor incapacity of the funding bodies, but behind the rapidly circulating project workforces stands the system to take away the power of the researchers over their agenda and to force them into a position that is not far away from *Ghost Work*.³⁴ Citizen Science, as a popular buzzword, would complement this in the way that scientific work would be de-qualified where possible and a reserve pool created with which Hanna could be reminded of her assigned place in case of doubt. Even for funding, alternatives based on the Kickstarter model are now often developed and sold as science startups, just like the organizational platforms of Citizen Science.

In this perspective, free public research is visibly transformed into a neoliberal science market with the Big 5 publishers as science platforms, which also pursue their own geopolitics, because they take over the validation for »elite research«, while the so-called predictive publishers as ragpickers sweep up the rest: non-English-speaking research, researchers of the Global South, periphery in every - also discipline-related - respect. These researchers, too, would need validation and would be thrown back on these infrastructures in the process. The contrast between legacy publishers and predictive publishers would thus not be one, because both would believe in the market in the same way, there would be sufficient financial space for both, and both would think little of ambitions of academia to determine content relevance to their discourse - »Let the market sort it out!«

³² Cf. Mirowski, Philip: *A Science Worth Trusting? Platform Capitalism Reorganizes the Science of the Future*. Presentation at Max Planck Institute for the History of Science, 18.01.2022, <https://www.mpiwg-berlin.mpg.de/video/science-worth-trusting-platform-capitalism-reorganizes-science-future>.

³³ Cf. Bahr, Amrei, Eichhorn, Kristin, Kubon, Sebastian: *#IchBinHanna. Prekäre Wissenschaft in Deutschland*. Frankfurt/M.: Suhrkamp 2022.

³⁴ Cf. Gray, Mary L., Suri, Siddharth: *Ghost Work. How to Stop Silicon Valley from Building a New Global Underclass*. Boston / New York: Houghton Mifflin Harcourt 2019.

4 Data Cartels

Mirowski does not yet see the major players in the science sector at the end of their plans, e.g., in the automation of practical laboratory operations, but extrapolates their more far-reaching ambitions from the current status. It is important to see that these ambitions are not limited to the science sector. The leading players in particular are spreading into other markets that are much larger still and promise similar revenues. In her book, Sarah Lamdan refers to these companies as *data cartels*³⁵ and considers RELX and Thomson Reuters as prime examples: they would not only be leaders in legal information, but relevant in all science communication, in financial and business information, in the news business, and increasingly as data brokers for the security industry. The business model would essentially always remain the same: a relevant public domain would be occupied and turned into a club good which, in view of the pricing, would then only be available to a privileged few.

Data cartels form a »GAFAM of curated information« and thus, for Lamdan, create a strong distortion in societal perception and self-assurance: the exclusive information is preferentially available to the decision-making level, while the broad mass of citizens, on the other hand, are increasingly restricted in managing their affairs in areas such as health, finance and rights. Tracking and the information it gathers would instead make them more and more the object of decisions, with sometimes devastating consequences: for example, in Michigan, the MiDAS automated decision-making system was introduced to track welfare fraud cases, and within a short time the number of suspected cases quintupled. However, almost all of the allegations were false, and by the time they were processed in court, many of those affected had lost their homes, had to file for bankruptcy, their marriages broke up, and some committed suicide.³⁶ Nevertheless, such systems continue to spread.³⁷

The decisive factor for this development is the long history of commercialization in connection with the neoliberal understanding of the state mentioned by Mirowski. The duopoly of RELX and Thomson Reuters in U.S. legal information developed precisely from the fact that the public sector allowed the print age to expire in the relevant legal resources without making any effort to find an adequate digital continuation. As a result, in Lamdan's account, the average *law firm* must spend 70% of its revenue on products from RELX and / or Thomson Reuters, which are becoming more law-shaping through their increasing enforcement with assistance and recommender functions. Likewise, those tracked by the militarized Immigration and Customs Enforcement (ICE) border police through the *Risk Solutions* data products of RELX and Thomson Reuters are reliant on the digital *Prison Products* of the same companies - and are those computer workstations in turn equipped with tracking technologies.³⁸ This is a prime example of the »extraction imperative« described by Zuboff, which also characterizes service platforms

³⁵ Sarah Lamdan: *Data Cartels. The Companies that Control and Monopolize Our Information*. Stanford, California: Stanford University Press 2022.

³⁶ See Gilman, Michelle: *AI Algorithms Intended to Root Out Welfare Fraud Often End Up Punishing the Poor Instead*. *The Conversation* Feb. 18, 2020, <https://www.nextgov.com/ideas/2020/02/ai-algorithms-intended-root-out-welfare-fraud-often-end-punishing-poor-instead/163166/>.

³⁷ De La Garza, Alejandro: *States' Automated Systems Are Trapping Citizens in Bureaucratic Nightmares With Their Lives on the Line*. *Time* May 28, 2020, <https://time.com/5840609/algorithm-unemployment/>.

³⁸ On the systematic nature of these prosecutions, see Georgetown Law Center on Privacy & Technology: *American Dragnet. Data-driven Deportation in the 21st Century*. <https://americandragnet.org/>.

increasingly in use in academia: The analysis of extracted usage data leads to new products that generate additional data, which in turn is analyzed and monetized until the workflows resemble a succession of Matryoshka dolls, all increasingly beholden to their own agendas instead of research or other public domains.

On reflection, perhaps little has done as much damage in the digital realm as the still-common phrase of data as the »new oil«. The person who hammers his hoe into the ground, starts up the drilling station or the excavator, is not met by data like oil, coal or ores. Data are artifacts associated with specific people: a specific person has taken a measurement, a device or service has logged usage data from another specific person. Talk of the new oil uncritically adopts surveillance capitalism's fundamental drive not to respect people's personal and inner connection to data, but to exploit and thus degrade it as alleged *virgin wood*. It is a colonial attitude turned into the digital,³⁹ just as classical colonialism declared and appropriated whole continents such as Australia as »no man's land« while exhibiting inhabitants of colonized areas as a »human zoo«. ⁴⁰ Data colonialism executes this in a novel way on a global scale, whether by promoting persecution and pogroms in the Global South,⁴¹ be it also in the countries of former colonial masters, where power and distribution struggles are exacerbated, often veiled by *culture wars*.

Here, too, tracking plays no insignificant role, since targeting can at least influence political competition, as was seen with *Cambridge Analytica*.⁴² Most importantly, it underpins the *alternative facts* ecosystem⁴³ with lots and lots of money: an estimated \$80 billion to \$120 billion, or about one-fifth of the global budget for tracking-based digital advertising, disappears every year through adfraud, funding organized crime, authoritarian regimes, some of which otherwise have difficulty obtaining foreign currency, and extremist movements. By 2025, adfraud is predicted by Hoffman to be the world's second most important source of money for criminals after drug trafficking.⁴⁴ Steve Bannon and his campaign slogan „Flood the zone with shit!“ is a well-known example of how hate speech can be financed with advertising money,⁴⁵ but initiatives like *#StopFundingHate* provide new evidence every day of how Russian propaganda against the Western world can also be turned into a business by Western money.⁴⁶ Whoever therefore brings AdTech tools like tracking into the scientific discourse is thus carrying science into a biotope where all core principles of good scientific practice and the self-

³⁹ See Couldry, Nick, Mejias, Ulises A.: *The Costs of Connection. How Data is Colonizing Human Life and Appropriating It for Capitalism*. Stanford, California: Stanford University Press 2019.

⁴⁰ Cf. Dreesbach, Anne: *Kolonialausstellungen, Völkerschauen und die Zurschaustellung des »Fremden«*. European History Online 17.02.2012, <https://ieg-ego.eu/de/threads/hintergruende/europaeische-begegnungen/anne-dreesbach-kolonialausstellungen-voelkerschauen-und-die-zurschaustellung-des-fremden>.

⁴¹ See, for example, Amnesty International's report on Facebook's role in the pogroms in Myanmar: *The social atrocity: Meta and the right to remedy for the Rohingya*. London: Amnesty 2022, <https://www.amnesty.org/en/documents/ASA16/5933/2022/en/>.

⁴² Cf. Wylie, Christopher: *Mindf*ck. Wie die Demokratie durch Social Media untergraben wird*. Köln: DuMont 2020.

⁴³ Cf. Kumkar, Nils C.: *Alternative Fakten. Zur Praxis der kommunikativen Erkenntnisverweigerung*. Frankfurt/M.: Suhrkamp 2022.

⁴⁴ Cf. Hoffman 2022, p. 38.

⁴⁵ See Jammi, Nandini; Atkin, Claire: *Steve Bannon is getting by with a little help from the world's biggest ad agencies. Check my ads 05/31/2021*; <https://checkmyads.org/branded/steve-bannon-is-getting-by-with-a/>

⁴⁶ Cf. <https://stopfundinghate.ch/> and <https://stopfundinghate.info/>.

enlightenment of a free society count for nothing, except instrumentally and as one opportunity for monetization among others.

5 Conclusion

„Demanding privacy from surveillance capitalists [...] or lobbying for an end to commercial surveillance on the internet is like asking old Henry Ford to make each Model T by hand. It's like asking a giraffe to shorten its neck, or a cow to give up chewing. These demands are existential threats that violate the basic mechanisms of the entity's survival.“⁴⁷ It is the business model of a cow not only to chew grass, but to chew it again and again until the last nutrient is sucked out. The same applies to the relationship of digital corporations to personal data.

Therefore, one does not have to adopt Mirowski's criticism of the neoliberal science model in detail, but nevertheless, in view of current developments, also in the field of Artificial Intelligence, the time of a quasi-naïve Open Science approach should be over. OpenAI (and competing companies) appropriated the training material without regard to the producers⁴⁸ and pays the descendants of former colonies pennies to clear hate and toxic content from its products,⁴⁹ but itself works on hidden watermarks to be able to maintain control.⁵⁰ Just as there can be no retreat into a »closed« approach in science, as this would only exclusively privilege the well-known specialized data cartels, so an open science model cannot be content to merely pander as *Mechanical Turk* to actors who have a relationship to the core values of science that is cynical at best. „The tech industry has hijacked a variety of commons and then rents us access to what should be open.“⁵¹ This »open« must be filled in a common good oriented way to resolve the current *Tragedy of the Commons* in its decimation to club property.⁵²

At the moment, however, it does not look like this will happen, but rather that the information sector will fall to the platforms in the foreseeable future, because the public sector will no longer be able to support it for demographic reasons alone. According to German Statistical Office, there were 11,407 employees at German university libraries in 2011, but only 9,442 ten

⁴⁷ Naughton, John: „The goal is to automate us“: welcome to the age of surveillance capitalism. The Guardian Jan. 20, 2019, <https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2019/jan/20/shoshana-zuboff-age-of-surveillance-capitalism-google-facebook>.

⁴⁸ Cf. James Vincent: The lawsuit that could rewrite the rules of AI copyright. The Verge 8.11.2022, <https://www.theverge.com/2022/11/8/23446821/microsoft-openai-github-copilot-class-action-lawsuit-ai-copyright-violation-training-data> and the websites <https://stablediffusionlitigation.com/> and <https://haveibeentrained.com/>.

⁴⁹ See Perrigo, Billy: OpenAI Used Kenyan Workers on Less Than \$2 Per Hour to Make ChatGPT Less Toxic. Time Jan. 18, 2023, <https://time.com/6247678/openai-chatgpt-kenya-workers/>. On the systematic nature of this approach, see Gray / Suri 2019.

⁵⁰ See Wiggers, Kyle: OpenAI's attempts to watermark AI text hit limits. TechCrunch 10.12.2022, <https://techcrunch.com/2022/12/10/openais-attempts-to-watermark-ai-text-hit-limits/>.

⁵¹ Monroe, Dwayne: ChatGPT: Super Rentier. Computational Impacts Jan. 20, 2023, <https://monroelab.net/chatgpt-super-rentier>.

⁵² Cf. Hardin, Garrett: The Tragedy of the Commons. Science Vol. 162, Issue 3859 (1968), pp. 1243 - 1248. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.162.3859.1243> and for the field of information Brintzinger, Klaus-Rainer: Piraterie oder Allmende der Wissenschaften? Zum Streit um Open Access und der Rolle von Wissenschaft, Bibliotheken und Markt bei der Verbreitung von Forschungsergebnissen. Leviathan Vol. 38 (2010), pp. 331 - 346. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11578-010-0095-5>.

years later.⁵³ At the same time, specialist training and thus the next generation of professionals is facing significant difficulties,⁵⁴ even though the real demographic wave is still to come, when in Germany 500,000 more people leave the labor market than enter it every year from around 2030 (migration effects, insofar as they can be reasonably forecast, are already included).⁵⁵ The public sector will then find itself in much fiercer competition with the private sector for human resources than it already is, but it will also have to differentiate itself internally. Since, for example, it cannot be assumed that tax collection will be terminated at some point for personnel reasons, the personnel pressure will probably be passed on to areas that do not belong to the very narrow sovereign sphere.

Such a development will, despite all the discussions about digital sovereignty, privilege the providers of »turnkey solutions« because they enable outsourcing driven by staff shortages (and thus recourse to a process that has been established since the neoliberal turn), and a look at the workbenches shows that this involves not only a model of »library-as-a-service« but an entire ecosystem of core university processes. The focus on big deals and transformational contracts in librarianship fosters this perspective, as the deliberate prioritization of major players and centralization of key functions will facilitate a smooth transition. The information sector could thus become a pioneer of *people farming*⁵⁶ on campus; the debate around #IchBinHanna already provides a taste of this.

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Surveillance capitalism is viewed very critically in Europe: the right to be forgotten, the General Data Protection Regulation as a whole, and a number of other regulatory interventions sprang from a social context in which the memory of the panoptic threat is as vivid as that of its mastermind. Jeremy Bentham decreed to be prepared after his death. This was done, and since 1850 he has been on display in the University College of London, whose foundation he inspired, in his clothes and with hat and walking stick, sitting on a chair. When Rector Sir Malcolm Grant retired in 2013, Bentham attended the council meeting. According to legend, in such cases the minutes of the meeting record Bentham as »present, but not voting.«⁵⁷ For raising one's voice is the task of all those who are interested in the reasonable development of free societies.

⁵³ Cf. Destatis: Personal an Hochschulen - Fachserie 11 Reihe 4.4, Ausgaben 2019 und 2021, p. 18. <https://www.destatis.de/DE/Themen/Gesellschaft-Umwelt/Bildung-Forschung-Kultur/Hochschulen/Publikationen/Downloads-Hochschulen/personal-hochschulen-2110440197004.html>

⁵⁴ Cf. Pfeffer, Magnus: No Future? Konsequenzen der Bewerberkrise der informationswissenschaftlichen Studiengänge. Bibliothek Forschung und Praxis Vol. 46, Issue 3 (2022), pp. 422 - 430. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1515/bfp-2022-0044>

⁵⁵ Cf. Stefan Schulz: Die Altenrepublik. Wie der demographische Wandel unsere Zukunft gefährdet. Köln: Hoffmann & Campe 2022.

⁵⁶ Cf. for an overview Wolfie Christl: Digitale Überwachung und Kontrolle am Arbeitsplatz. From the Expansion of Operational Data Collection to Algorithmic Management? Vienna: Cracked Labs 2021, <https://crackedlabs.org/daten-arbeitsplatz/info> and related to higher education processes Swauger, Shea: The next normal: Algorithms will take over college, from admissions to advising. The Washington Post 12 Nov. 2021, https://www.washingtonpost.com/outlook/next-normal-algorithms-college/2021/11/12/366fe8dc-4264-11ec-a3aa-0255edc02eb7_story.html

⁵⁷ <https://metro.co.uk/2013/07/12/181-year-old-corpse-of-jeremy-bentham-attends-ucl-board-meeting-3879586/>